

ICCAR 2024 PROGRAM

Session 1.1			10 NOVEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-1	09:00-09:10	HELD IN SOME REGIONS OF AZERBAIJAN GENETIC-SELECTION STUDIES OF FRUIT PLANTS	Asadova Basti	Azerbaijan	Mail Submission 1
Y-2	09:10-09:20	HUMAN GENE CLONING AND PROTEIN EXPRESSION	Asadova Basti	Azerbaijan	Mail Submission 2
Y-3	09:20-09:30	Complete Controllability of Impulsive Semilinear Differential Equations in Fréchet Spaces	Abdelhamid Bensalem	Algeria	Submission 679
Y-4	09:30-09:40	On the Cauchy Problem for Nonlinear Fractional Systems with Lipschitzian Matrices Under the Generalized Metric Spaces	Abdelatif Boutiara	Algeria	Submission 680
Y-5	09:40-09:50	Implementation of School-Based Management in the Context of National Education	Tetty Suriani, Daniel Polii, Doni Abadi Nababan	Indonesia, Indonesia, Indonesia	Submission 682
Y-6	09:50-10:00	Study of Failure of Laminated Composites VERRE E/EPOXY	Adel Deliou, Abdelkader Fidjah, Meriem Dehbi, Khmissi Belkaid, Mohamed Chaour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 683
Y-7	10:00-10:10	Novel Selenium-NHC Complexes and Benzimidazolium Salts' Antimicrobial Properties: Synthesis and Mechanistic Understanding	Boutheina BOUALIA, Abd el-krim SANDELI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 684
Y-8	10:10-10:20	High-Temperature Effect on Mechanical Properties of GGBS-Based Geopolymer Composites Having Bauxite Residue	Shahir Ahmad Safi, Ali Raza, Mujib Ul Rahman Rahmani, Abdellatif Selmi	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia	Submission 686
Y-9	10:20-10:30	Theoretical Assessment and Molecular Docking of an Organic Compound for Anticancer Drug Design	Nour Eddine Benharkat, Abdelkader Chouaih, Nourdine Boukabcha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 687
Y-10	10:30-10:40	Geometrical, topological, and dynamical description of N interacting spin-particles in a long-range Ising model	Brahim Amghar, Mohammed Daoud	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 691

Session 1.2			10 NOVEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-11	09:00-09:10	Reinforcement of Sandy Soils Using Fibers Based on Recycled Waste	Lina ZAIDI, Fatima Zohra BEN AMARA, Issam MESBAHI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 693
Y-12	09:10-09:20	Effect of nonthermal Polarization Force on Double Layer Structures in a Dusty Plasma	Besma Belaifa	Algeria	Submission 696
Y-13	09:20-09:30	FMOs and UV-Vis Absorption Spectra, Global and Local Chemical Reactivity and Mulliken atomic charges of new hydrazone derivative	Samia DJABBOUR, Nourdine BOUKABCHA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 698
Y-14	09:30-09:40	Weakly Asymptotically Almost Automorphic Solutions of Integro-Differential Equations in Banach Spaces with Respect to Weak Topologies	Nadia Ikhlef	Algeria	Submission 701
Y-15	09:40-09:50	The optical properties of bilayer structures	Widad LOUAFI, Karim REZOUALI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 702
Y-16	09:50-10:00	Impact of Elevated Temperature and Salt Solutions on Mechanical Strength of Geopolymer Concrete	Shahir Ahmad Safi, Ali Raza, Reshteen Ahmad Hemat, Abdellatif Selmi, Mujib Ul Rahman Rahmani	Pakistan, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 704
Y-17	10:00-10:10	Analysis of trends in the well jet pumps development	Oleksandr Panevnyk	Ukraine	Submission 705
Y-18	10:10-10:20	Outage performance of a RIS-assisted network in a Hoyt fading environment	Slimane Benmahmoud, Nora Ougueni, El-Hadi Meftah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 707
Y-19	10:20-10:30	Channel Estimation for a SISO Visible Light Communications System: A Comparative Study of Five Estimators	Slimane Benmahmoud, Nora Ougueni, Brahim Dehri, El-Hadi Meftah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 708
Y-20	10:30-10:40	Role of Artificial Intelligence in Enhancing Quality of Higher Education in Algeria	Hiba MERKOUNE, Hizia MERKOUNE	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 711

Session 1.3			10 NOVEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-21	10:00-10:10	Design and Control of Wind Turbine Systems Using Dual Stator Induction Generators for Enhanced Power Output	Khaled Benzaoui, Mohammed Boukhari	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 712
Y-22	10:10-10:20	Synthesis, Molecular Docking, Hirshfeld Surface Analysis, Energy Framework, NCI-RDG, and Theoretical Calculations of a New Thiazolidine Compound	Khaled Drim, Youcef Megrouss, Mohammed Amin Benaouda, Mansour Azayez	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 716
Y-23	10:20-10:30	A Novel Open-Switch Fault Diagnosis Method in a Vector-Controlled PMSM Drive	Hicham Zaimen, Mouatez Billah Guendouze, Said Touati, Ali Rezig	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 717
Y-24	10:30-10:40	Maintaining the integrity of petroleum pilot wells by formulating new cement based on hydrophobic materials	ZAKARIA Adjou, DJAMILA Boufades, MUSTAPHA Miloudi, SOUAD Hammadou née Mesdour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 718
Y-25	10:40-10:50	INVESTIGATION OF STRUCTURAL AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF MANGANESE DOPED COBALT FERRITE/gCN COMPOSITES	Areej Fatima, Hafeez Anwar	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 720
Y-26	10:50-11:00	Systematic Analysis of Nonlinear Fractional Differential Equations Using Caputo's q-Derivative	Houari BOUZID, Abdelkader BENALI, Omar ALIMERINA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 721
Y-27	11:00-11:10	Optimizing Electrocatalysts for Hydrogen Production through Water Electrolysis: A Simulation Approach	Hizia MERKOUNE	Algeria	Submission 730
Y-28	11:10-11:20	"Numerical Approache to Reaction-Diffusion Model Applied in Biology:	Samiha Djemai, Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 731
Y-29	11:20-11:30	A Focus on Convergence Analysis"	Samiha Djemai, Salim Mesbahi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 732
Y-30	11:30-11:40	Exploring Periodic Solutions in Stochastic Reaction-Diffusion Neural Networks: Insights and Applications	Mohamed Lakhder GUESMI, Mohamed GUESMI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 733

Session 1.4			10 NOVEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-31	10:00-10:10	Advances in Passive Microfluidic Techniques for Sustainable Biodiesel Production	Fouad Jumaah Luaibi Al-saedi, Morteza Bayareh	Iran, Iran	Submission 734
Y-32	10:10-10:20	Chemical Profile of Achillea Millefolium plants by Using Head Space Technique	Jonida Salihila, Aida Dama, Kleva Shpati, Aurora Napuce, Aurel Nuro	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 735
Y-33	10:20-10:30	Exploring Non-Newtonian Flow Dynamics in Microchannels: Fundamentals and Applications	Hasan Falah Abdulhasan, Morteza Bayareh	Iran, Iran	Submission 736
Y-34	10:30-10:40	A Hybrid Blockchain and PKI Solution for Robust Authentication in the Internet of Vehicles	BENADLA Sarra, DEBBAL Mohammed, BENADLA Nadjet	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 738
Y-35	10:40-10:50	Existence and uniqueness results of solutions for a multi-point Riemann-Liouville fractional boundary value problem (RL-FBVP)	Ait Mohammed Hicham, Mezabia Mohamed Elhadi, Tellab Brahim	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 739
Y-36	10:50-11:00	Comparative Analysis of Gentian Violet Dye Adsorption Using Agro-Waste-Derived Activated Carbon and Commercial Nanoparticles	FERROUDJ Nawal, Labeled Amel, TRODI Amira	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 740
Y-37	11:00-11:10	Design and Optimization of a WDM-PON Based Optical Access Network for High-Speed Applications	DEBBAL Mohammed, MENEZLA Fayssal, BOUREGAA Mouweffeq	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 741
Y-38	11:10-11:20	New Approach for Characterization and Mitigation of the Swelling Phenomenon	Chaima Mahkour	Algeria	Submission 742
Y-39	11:20-11:30	The Energy Consumption and its linkage with Crude Oil, Natural Gas and Electricity Generation in GCC states	Ahmed Saddam Abdulsahib	Oman	Submission 744
Y-40	11:30-11:40	Evaluation of the Adsorption Efficiency of Basic Fuchsin Dye Using a Laboratory-Synthesized Phytoadsorbent	Nessrine Mechraoui, Mebrouk Djedid, Mokhtar Benalia, Asma Boudaoud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 749

Session 1.5			10 NOVEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-41	11:00-11:10	Reviewing the Role of Waste Materials in Soil Reinforcement: Innovations and Applications	Muhammad Haseeb, Anas Ayub, Aimen Nawaz	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 753
Y-42	11:11-11:20	Biodiesel Production Using KOH and NaOH Catalysts: A Comparative Study	Abdelhalim BALOULI, Tarek BERRAMA, Hayet TIZI, Feriel SAHOUI, Aimen MARIR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 754
Y-43	11:20-11:30	Detection and Safety Evaluation of Pesticide Residues in Strawberries from Algeria Using QuEChERS and UPLC/QTOF	Souad Hammadou née Mesdour, Djamila Boufades, Zakaria Adjou, Mustapha Miloudi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 758
Y-44	11:30-11:40	Effect of Viscoelastic dampers on Earthquake Resistance of High-Rise Building	Muhammad Yaqub, Kawajah Salman Majid, Waqar Shafique, Muhammad Ausaf Rai, Muhammad Hamza	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 761
Y-45	11:40-11:50	Evaluation of Slope Stability Using the Lower and Upper Limit Analysis Method with Study Parametric of Faults (Shear Joints)	Guemidi Ismahene, Taleb Hosni Abderrahmane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 763
Y-46	11:50-12:00	Monitoring Land Use Change and Vegetation Dynamics by Remote Sensing in the Semi-Arid Zone of the Ouled Sidi Yahia Forest (Algeria)	Laila Naib, Djilali Baghdadi, Amaria Belarbi, Laid Bouchaala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 765
Y-47	12:00-12:10	Evaluation Of Energy and Thermal Performance For Residential Buildings	Meroua Kertous, Abdellah Zerroug, Nadjat Zerroug	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 768
Y-48	12:10-12:20	Impact of the W/C Ratio on the Physico-Mechanical and Rheological Characteristics of High-Performance Concrete Made with Natural Pozzolana	Guemidi Ismahene, Taleb Hosni Abderrahmane	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 771
Y-49	12:20-12:30	Drug delivery using hydrogel films based on polymers	Oumamar Loubna*, Soltani El Khamza, KHALIL KAOUANE, AYOUB BEKKA, KEMCHACHE HAMZA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 773
Y-50	12:30-12:40	Advancements in Machine Learning for Handwritten Text Recognition	Fella Berrimi	Algeria	Submission 775

Session 1.6			10 NOVEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-51	11:00-11:10	Evaluating the Impact of Limestone on the Strength and Durability of Virgin Cork Concrete	Samah Hariz, Fouad Ghomari, Brahim Touil	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 776
Y-52	11:11-11:20	Investigation of Structural Stability and Magnetic Properties of CoF ₂ Using Ab Initio Methods and High Temperature Series Expansions	Rachid Masrouf	Morocco	Submission 777
Y-53	11:20-11:30	Magnetism and phase transitions in CoFe ₂ O ₄	Rachid Masrouf	Morocco	Submission 778
Y-54	11:30-11:40	Electronic and magnetic properties of PrAg : Ab initio calculations and High Temperature Series Expansions	Rachid Masrouf	Morocco	Submission 779
Y-55	11:40-11:50	Entomofauna inventory in an olive orchard in M'Sila (Northeast Algeria)	Mimeche Hayet, Chafaa Smail, Laabassi Ayache, Mimeche Fateh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 780
Y-56	11:50-12:00	Modified Bathe–Noh method for implicit time integration approach featuring adjustable digital dissipation	L. Beghdadi, A. Beghdadi, R. Kouli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 785
Y-57	12:00-12:10	Laboratory study of the influence of silica and clay nanoparticles in chemical flooding to improve residual oil recovery	ZAKARIA Adjou, DJAMILA Boufades, MUSTAPHA Miloudi, SOUAD Hammadou Née Mesdour	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 786
Y-58	12:10-12:20	Analysis and Characterization of Next-Generation PON Networks Using OptiSystem Simulation	BOUREGAA Mouweffeq, DEBBAL Mohammed , BENGANA Abdelfatih, BEMMOUSSAT Chems Eddine	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 787
Y-59	12:20-12:30	Novel Optical Filtering Approach for Inter-Channel Interference Reduction in optical communication Systems	TOUAOULA Hachem, BABA-AHMED Mohammed Zakarya, DEBBAL Mohammed , MENEZLA Fayssal, BOUREGAA Mouweffeq	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 789
Y-60	12:30-12:40	Evaluation of Oxidative Stress Biomarker GSH in Rat liver and kidney damaged by a Dithiocarbamate fungicide: Propineb	Merghad I., Grara N., Merghad A.	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 795

Session 1.7			10 NOVEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-61	12:00-12:10	The Importance of Trademark Registration Process	Endi Kalemaj, Kejsi Marku	Albania, Albania	Submission 797
Y-62	12:11-12:20	Transforming Waste into Resources: Pioneering Approaches in Civil Engineering	BOUSLAH Mahmoud, MAZA Mekki, RAHMOUNI Zine EL Abidine, TEBBAL Nadia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 800
Y-63	12:20-12:30	Effects of Interface Roughness on the Bearing Capacity of Strip Foundations with Skirts	Fouzi Mancer, Mohamed Sadak Merrakchi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 801
Y-64	12:30-12:40	Impact of Friction Angle on Circular Skirted Footing Performance on a Layer of Sand	Fouzi Mancer, Mohamed Sadak Merrakchi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 802
Y-65	12:40-12:50	Performance Analysis of Circular Skirted Foundations under Vertical Load	Fouzi Mancer, Mohamed Sadak Merrakchi	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 803
Y-66	12:50-13:00	Backing-plate influence on the static behaviour of T-stubs: a numerical approach	Mohammed Mokhtar FEKIR, Hichem Rakib SEBBAGH, Zakaria BENARBA, Anis ABIDELAH	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 804
Y-67	13:00-13:10	Seismic performance evaluation of high-rise building in Multan city using “Autodesk ROBOT Structural Analysis”	Tahir Sultan, Hafiz Muhammad Saud, Abdul Waqar Rajput, Muhammad Umer Farooq, Ahmad Faraz	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 809
Y-68	13:10-13:20	Induction of myocardial infarction by isoproterenol and the preventive effect of pomegrates punicalagin against inflammation, oxidative stress and apoptosis in rats myocardiocytes	Zehoura Lekroun, Mohamed Kebieche, Djamila Zama	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 811
Y-69	13:20-13:30	Detection of Cymothoid Isopods in three commercially fish species of Albanian coastal waters	Enkeleda Ozuni, Egon Andoni, Dorian Beqiraj, Pellumb Zalla, Rezart Postoli, Majlind Sulce, Albana Munga, Blerina Luke, Ilir Dova	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 815
Y-70	13:30-13:40	Numerical Insights into Perovskite Solar Cell Performance with a Delafossite-Based HTL	Nabil Bouri	Morocco	Submission 816

Session 1.8			10 NOVEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-71	12:00-12:10	A Robust Sensor-less Fuzzy Logic Control Strategy for BLDC Motor Using Sliding Mode Observation	Dehmeche Ibrahim, Kechida Ridha, Bouzidi Riad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 817
Y-72	12:11-12:20	Comparative Study of the Structural Behavior of Welded and Rolled T-Stub in Metal Assemblies under Elevated Temperature Conditions	Yasmina DOUAH, Anis Abidelah, SEBBAGH Hichem Rakib, Djamel Eddin KERDAL	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 818
Y-73	12:20-12:30	Synthesis and Characterization of (2-hydroxyethyl)trimethylammonium Ionic Liquid: A Study Integrating NMR, FT-IR, and DFT Calculations	Aya Khadidja Touil, Silvia Antonia Brandan, María V. Castillo, Boumediene Haddad, Annalisa Paolone, Bekhaled Fetouhi, Nathalie Bar, Didier Villemin, Mustapha Rahmouni, Serge Bresson	Algeria, Argentina, Argentina, France, Italy, Algeria, France, France, Algeria, France	Submission 826
Y-74	12:30-12:40	Nanoencapsulation of Sodium Diclofenac by Chitosan poly (acrylic acid) Matrix to control delivery	Abir Derbali, Djallel Bouzid, Amel Sadji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 829
Y-75	12:40-12:50	A Comprehensive Review of Prediction Methods for Fatigue Crack Life in Welded Structures: Focus on Cyclic Plasticity in Steels	Zain Ali, Adeel Ahmad, Areej Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 831
Y-76	12:50-13:00	Connectivity of Weak Rock Zones: A Review of Its Role in Mining-Induced Deformation of Rock Slopes	Zain Ali, Areej Ahmed, Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 832
Y-77	13:00-13:10	Dynamic Liquefaction Assessment: A Comprehensive Review of Triaxial Testing Methods for Soils with Variable Saturation.	Zain Ali, Muneeb Hassan, Areej Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 833
Y-78	13:10-13:20	Evaluating Small Strain Deformation Mechanisms in Consolidated Sand: A Micromechanical Perspective	Zain Ali, Usama Munir, Areej Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 834
Y-79	13:20-13:30	Flood Economics in Urban Landscapes: A Review of Reconstruction Challenges and Solutions	Zain Ali, Areej Ahmed, Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 835
Y-80	13:30-13:40	Strengthening Against Shakes : A Review on Methods for Evaluating Seismic Capacity of Concrete Structures	Zain Ali, Areej Ahmed, Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 836

Session 1.9			10 NOVEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-81	13:00-13:10	Evaluation of Hardness and Corrosion Behavior of An AA 7175 aluminum alloy in Sulfuric Acid Environment	Ali DEBIH	Algeria	Submission 850
Y-82	13:11-13:20	Teaching Strategies and Technology in Higher Education in Kosovo	Shqiponja NALLBANI-BERISHA	Kosovo	Submission 864
Y-83	13:20-13:30	Securing Underwater Internet of Things Communications: An Integrated ECDH and PKI Approach for Enhanced Radar Data Protection	Sebbah Abderrezzak, Fekar Mohammed Riyadh El Mansour	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 873
Y-84	13:30-13:40	Mechanical Strength Properties of Portland Pozzolana Green Cement Nanocomposites	Fatima Zahra, Abdellatif Selmi, Ali Raza	Pakistan, Tunisia, Pakistan	Submission 884
Y-85	13:40-13:50	Advances in Project Management for Civil Engineering: A Review of Digital and Technological Interventions	Areej Ahmed, Zain Ali, Adeel Ahmad	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 902
Y-86	13:50-14:00	Revolutionizing Construction : A Critical Review of BIM Technologies and Their Impact on the Industry	Adeel Ahmed, Zain Ali, Areej Ahmed	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 906
Y-87	14:00-14:10	Presence of Caprine Arthritis Encephalitis in goats in Lezhë County, Albania	Doriana Beqiraj, Brixhilda Qyra, Enkeleda Ozuni, Albana Munga, Pëllumb Zalla, Egon Andoni, Gerald Muça, Ilir Dova, Valentin Shtjefni, Majlind Sulçe	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 922
Y-88	14:10-14:20	The computational analysis of the inclusion complex formed between curcumin and Hydroxypropyl β -cyclodextrin using methods such as DFT, QTAIM, NCI-RDG, and DM	Mostefai Noria, Abdelkrim Guendouzi, Fatima Yahia Cherif	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 840
Y-89	14:20-14:30	Optimizing Feed-Forward Neural Networks Using Particle Swarm Optimization for Improved Convergence and Accuracy	Soufiane Benhammoud, Ziyad Bouchama, Khalissa Behih, Adem Guenifi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 843
Y-90	14:30-14:40	Optimizing BLDC Motor Control in Electric Vehicles Using Robust Predictive Strategies	Dehmeche Ibrahim, Kechida Ridha, Bouzidi Riad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 857

Session 1.10			10 NOVEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-91	13:00-13:10	ADRC-Based Torque Ripple Minimization for Enhanced Induction Motor Performance in Electric Vehicle Applications	Anwar Zorig, Ahmed Belkheiri, Katia Kouzi, Mohammed Belkheiri	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 858
Y-92	13:11-13:20	Charged rotating AdS black hole with quintessence	H. Laassiri, A. Daassou, R. Benbrik	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 860
Y-93	13:20-13:30	Thermodynamic properties of Bardeen-AdS black holes with a dark field	H. Laassiri, A. Daassou, R. Benbrik	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 865
Y-94	13:30-13:40	Impact of Superhydrophobic Coatings on Electric Field Distribution in High-Voltage Insulators Under Moist Conditions	ALOUACHE Sara, MEDJDOUB Abdellah, BELHOUL Talit	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 867
Y-95	13:40-13:50	Kerr–Newman AdS black holes in Rastall gravity with dark matter	H. Laassiri, A. Daassou, R. Benbrik	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 868
Y-96	13:50-14:00	Enhancing MQTT Performance: A Novel Semantic-Aware Transport Layer Protocol for Smart Cities	Lokesh Kumar, Kousar Khatoon	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 872
Y-97	14:00-14:10	GRAPHENE in Fractional-Dimensional Space	MERAD ASMA, MERAD SARA	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 876
Y-98	14:10-14:20	A Comparative DFT Study of Bonding and Reactivity in Transition Metal Complexes	Sara MERAD, Asma MERAD, Sabri MECHERI, BACHIR ZOUCOUNE, Abdallah ZAITER	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 880
Y-99	14:20-14:30	Optimization of the Selective Flotation of a Collective Pre-Concentrate of Zinc and Pyrite: Case Study of "Chaabat-El-Hamra Mines, Setif"	Chouafa Mohamed, Benabbes Khaled, Belhaoues Saber, Trirat Tabet, Rahim Ouahab5, Yahi Taki, Arif Saleh, Alirachdi Sofiane, Becheker Ali, Allem Mohcen	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 766
Y-100	14:30-14:40	EVALUATION OF SELF-SENSING BEHAVIOR OF CONCRETE	H. Asfandyar Ahmed, M. Fahad	China, Pakistan	Submission 838

Session 1.11			10 NOVEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-101	14:00-14:10	Renewable energy hardening of concrete for maritime structures	BEN AMMAR Ben Khadda	Algeria	Submission 892
Y-102	14:11-14:20	Modeling of a direct current propulsion system	Abdelghafour HERIZI, Riyadh ROUABHI, Eloualid ZOUGGAR, Noureddine CHAMI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 893
Y-103	14:20-14:30	Influence of the Papanastasiou Regularization Parameter on the Evolution of Rigid Zones in Herschel-Bulkley Fluid Flow	Messaouda Elalem, Farid Messelmi, Hadi Taibi, Abdelaziz Rabehi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 894
Y-104	14:30-14:40	A parametric study of N ₂ /O ₂ DBD discharge temperature for ozone production	Amar BENMOUSSA, Ahmed BELASRI, Abdellah El hadj Adeland, Radja Nour El Imene Bennoui, Raghed Belbachir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 914
Y-105	14:40-14:50	Peanut consumption and the risk of developing an allergy	Imène Boualeg	Algeria	Submission 916
Y-106	14:50-15:00	New Insights into Gluten Allergy in Algeria	Imène Boualeg	Algeria	Submission 917
Y-107	15:00-15:10	Comparative Study of laminated and sandwich composite plate based on First-order shear deformation theory using p-element formulation	A BELAIDI, SMN SERDOUN, SA BELALIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 994
Y-108	15:10-15:20	Characterizations and Catalytic Activity of Fe-Modified MgO Nanostructures in Sono assisted degradation of of organic pollutant	Mania TERKI, Fatma AHNIA, Amel SADJI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 919
Y-109	15:20-15:30	SMEs Data Analyses in Albanian Economy - independent or controlled enterprises?	Elona Dashi (Berberi)	Albania	Submission 931
Y-110	15:30-15:40	Synthesis of Poly(o-ethylaniline)/TiO ₂ /rGO Composites for Photocatalytic Degradation of Direct Yellow 12 Dye	Mirza Nadeem Ahmad, Muhammad Fayyaz Farid, Muhammad Naveed Anjum	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 943

Session 1.12			10 NOVEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-111	14:00-14:10	Remote Project Management: Challenges, Tools, and Best Practices in the Digital Era	Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar, Muhammad Hamza Kaleem, Ahsan Habib	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 946
Y-112	14:11-14:20	Artificial Intelligence in Project Scheduling and Resource Allocation: Enhancing Efficiency and Accuracy	Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar, Muhammad Hamza Kaleem, Abdullah Sajjad	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 947
Y-113	14:20-14:30	Sustainable Practices in Construction Management: A Comprehensive Overview	Muhammad Hamza Kaleem, Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar, Muhammad Umer Qureshi	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 948
Y-114	14:30-14:40	Comparing VADER and BERT for Short-Text Sentiment Analysis: Challenges and Observed Variations	Ilma Lili, Endrit Xhina, Anxhela Kosta, Arbër Ceni, Mirvjen Ulqinaku	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 974
Y-115	14:40-14:50	Understanding the Impact of AI Techniques on Business Management and Process Automation	Anxhela Kosta, Endrit Xhina, Ilma Lili, Marjana Hida	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 982
Y-116	14:50-15:00	Role of Climate-Resilient Project Management Practices in Construction: Adaptive Approaches for Floods, Earthquakes, and High Temperatures	Asad Mahmood, Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram, Muhammad Hamza Kaleem	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 984
Y-117	15:00-15:10	CONCEPTION OF NEW METAMATERIAL BIOSENSOR FOR SKIN CANCER DIAGNOSIS AT TERAHERTZ BAND	T. Aliouar, D.Bensafieddine, F. Djerfaj, F.Bendelala	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 14
Y-118	15:10-15:20	Predictive Analysis of Shear Modulus in Geotextile-Reinforced Granular Sand Using Hybrid Modeling Techniques	Aymen Elouanas Asseli, Ismail Benessalah, Adam Hamrouni, Ayad Lounas, Seif Eddine Khadraoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 15
Y-119	15:20-15:30	Characterization Using Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) of Self-Compacting Concrete Made with Recycled Aggregates and Silica Fume	Omri Imen Yamina, Khadraoui Seif Eddine, Assli Aymen Elouanas	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 16
Y-120	15:30-15:40	Comparative study of titanium dioxide thin layer deposition techniques for photocatalysis applications	EL ALIOUI Sadik, Zakaria BARBOUCH, Abdellatif El-Habib, RMILI Ahmad	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Mail Submission 17

Session 1.13			10 NOVEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-121	15:00-15:10	Effect of fish feed on the growth and body composition of silver carps in brackish water	Muhammad Rizwan, Muhammad Mubashir Nazir, Nageen Niazi, Muhammad Saleem, Muhammad Muzammil Nazir	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Mail Submission 18
Y-122	15:11-15:20	Optimization of Conventional Extraction Techniques for Phenolic Compound Recovery and Antioxidant Potency in Algerian Myrtus communis L. Fruits: A Valorization Approach for Functional Food Ingredient Development	TAIBI Abdeslem, MOKRANI Abderrahmane, Fatiha HAMITRI-GUERFI, KADI Ahcene, TEFFANE Mohand, ARROUL Younes	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 19
Y-123	15:20-15:30	Antibacterial and antifungal potential of Streptomyces strain against pathogenic bacterial and fungal species	ARROUL Younes, BOUKHALFA Farid, OUFIGHOU Amira, TEFFANE Mohand, KADI Ahcene, TAIBI Abdeslem, HAMMA Samir, CHABANE Sabine, SIMOUD Yasmine, KACHA Mouloud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 20
Y-124	15:30-15:40	Association of DNA-Repair Gene Polymorphisms with Renal Failure Risk in the Iraqi Population: A Post-PCR Case-Control Analysis	Fahad D. F. Abo-Ghneim, Dhafer A. F. Al-Koofee, Hussain Jasem Mohammed	Iraq, Iraq, Iraq	Mail Submission 21
Y-125	15:40-15:50	A New Biomimetic Design Biomaterials for Bone Regeneration by TPMS Lattice Structure	M.R.Harroug, H.Ameddah, H. Mazouz	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 22
Y-126	15:50-16:00	Assessment of biological activities of secondary metabolites of Pseudomonas chlororaphis subsp. Aurantiaca	Salma Batool, Huma Samar, Iqra Abbas, Izzah Shahid, Samina Mehnaz, Burhan Haider	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Mail Submission 23
Y-127	16:00-16:10	Effect of Gurevich Polarization Force on Double-Layer Structures in a Collisionless Complex Plasma	Besma Belaifa, Moufida Benzekka	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 24
Y-128	16:10-16:20	Enhanced MPPT for PV Systems with Grey Wolf Optimization in Partial and Dynamic Shading Conditions	Feriel Abdelmalek, Hamza Afghoul, Fateh Krim, Djallal Eddine Zabia, Salah Anis Krim, Belgacem Med Nassim Bouzidi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 25
Y-129	16:20-16:30	DFT study and molecular docking simulation on sulfanilic acid and its derivatives: Antibacterial activity	Slimani Yasmine, Boukaoud Abdelali	Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 26
Y-130	16:30-16:40	Effect of temperature and storage on bioactive compounds of an Algerian spice saffron (crocus sativus)	Fatima TENSAOUT, Mostapha Bachir-bey, Djamel Eden KATI , Guerboub lynda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 27

Session 1.14			10 NOVEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-131	15:00-15:10	Study of -2-(4-(2-methylpropyl) phe)propanoic acid removal by Cu-Fe-layered double hydroxide from aqueous solution	R. Ghemit , A. Makhloufi, M. el Kolli	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 28
Y-132	15:11-15:20	SMART AGRICULTURE AN EFFICIENT WAY TO PRESERVE PLANT RESOURCES	FERFAR Meriem, DRIOUCHE Youssouf , MERAD Faycel, ABBASSI Hadj Ahmed	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 29
Y-133	15:20-15:30	Revolutionizing Construction: The Role and Challenges of Robotics and Automation in Pakistan's Construction Industry	Chaudhry Muhammad Shahram Akbar, Muhammad Hamza Kaleem, Awais Bashir	Pakistan, Pakistan, Pakistan	Mail Submission 30
Y-134	15:30-15:40	Analysis of functionally graded plates using refined high order shear deformation theory	MERDACI Slimane, HADJ MOSTEFA Adda, BOUCHAFA Ali	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 31
Y-135	15:40-15:50	Use of a natural activated adsorbent for wastewater treatment: Study of methylene blue adsorption	Rekia Louiza LAKHDARI , Nadia Aicha LAOUFI, Meriem AKKAR, Abdelkader Mouheb	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 32
Y-136	15:50-16:00	Impact of mineral additions on the fresh properties of high-performance concretes	Rahim Ouahab, Yahi Takai eddine, Afri Amira, Ali Rachedi Sofiane, Arif Salah, Trirat Tabet, Driouche Youssouf, Allem Mohcene	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 692
Y-137	16:00-16:10	Harnessing Waste for Eco-Conscious Insulation Materials	Sofiane Alirachedi, Zahra Mellouk, Linda Saily, Ouahab Rahim, Bedouh Yazid, Arif Saleh, Yahi Takai Eddine, Tabet Trirat, Chouafa Mohamed, Allem Mohcene, Benabbes Khaled	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 764
Y-138	16:10-16:20	Numerical study of unsteady flow in Herschel-Bulkley fluids	Messaouda Elalem, Farid Messelmi, Hadi Taibi, Abdelaziz Rabehe	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 920
Y-139	16:20-16:30	Effect of thermal treatment under vacuum of thermal sprayed aluminum coating on industrial carbon steel E335	Fatma AHNIA, Mania TERKI	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 923
Y-140	16:30-16:40	Chemical composition, antioxidant and antibacterial and neuroprotective activity of Algerian propolis	Soltani Yassamin, Aboura Amina, Arrar Zoheir	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 925

Session 1.15			10 NOVEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-141	16:00-16:10	The relationship between Organizational culture and knowledge creation	Abdelheq LACHACHI	Oman	Submission 930
Y-142	16:10-16:20	Driving Circular Economy: Investigating the Economic and Environmental Benefits of By-Products Exchange in Steel and Re-Rolling Industry of Islamabad, Pakistan	Aiza Javed	Pakistan	Submission 934
Y-143	16:20-16:30	An Empirical Model Evaluation for Predicting Membrane filtration Clogging	Cherifi leila, Ammi yamina, Hanini salah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 949
Y-144	16:30-16:40	Insight into the corrosion inhibition of new derivatives as highly efficient inhibitors for mild steel in 0.5 M HCl	Chibane Amina, Aliouane Nabila, Toukal Linda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 950
Y-145	16:40-16:50	Career commitment and organizational change. How career commitment affects employee's readiness for change	Gentisa Furxhi, Sonela Stillo, Marinela Teneqexhi	Albania, Albania, albania	Submission 953
Y-146	16:50-17:00	Ab intio calculations of semiconducting CdS	Chiraz Soundes Bouaita, Ali Hamidani, GHERBI Khouloud	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 954
Y-147	17:00-17:10	Design Optimization of Nanostructured Metamaterials for Improved Electrical Performance of PbS-CQD Solar Thermal Photovoltaic Cells	Oussama Baitiche, Fathi Bendellala, Ali Cheknane, Aissa Bellakhdar	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 955
Y-148	17:17-17:20	A DFT study on structural and electronic properties of hydrogenated silicene sheet	Khouloud GHERBI, Med Tahar KADRI, Hafid BELKHIR, Chiraz Soundes BOUAITA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 959
Y-149	17:20-17:30	Non-Destructive Techniques for Quantifying Desiccation Cracks in Clay Soils: A Review	Afaf Zeroual, Amina Masmoudi, Ahmed Bouaziz, Sadok Feia, Abdelali Dadda	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 964
Y-150	17:30-17:40	Study of genomic parameters in elderly individuals by influence of peptide bioregulator	Gaiozishvili Maia, Buadze Tamar	Georgia, Georgia	Submission 965

Session 1.16			10 NOVEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-151	16:00-16:10	Capability of Roman Space Telescope to detect quasar microlensing	Lindita Hamolli, Esmeralda Guliqani, Mimoza Hafizi	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 970
Y-152	16:10-16:20	Synthesis, Structural Characterization, and Electrocatalytic Performance of NiFe ₂ O ₄ /Graphene Oxide Composite	Nighat Javed, Kiran Aftab	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 985
Y-153	16:20-16:30	Strong Lensing by a Singular Isothermal Ellipsoid Galaxy	Esmeralda Guliqani, Lindita Hamolli, Mimoza Hafizi	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 990
Y-154	16:30-16:40	Using Space Syntax to a comparative Evaluation of Walkability, Vernacular vs contemporary Urban Spaces of Arid Regions	Fouzia Meliouh, Khalissa Hamel, Faten Ghanemi, Mohamed Yahia Amran Necib	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 995
Y-155	16:40-16:50	The assessment of how building density influences microclimate conditions and occupant well-being in the Algerian oasis	Khalissa Hamel, Fouzia Meliouh, Mohamed Yahia Amran Necib	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 996
Y-156	16:50-17:00	Optimizing Courtyard Geometries for Enhanced Natural Lighting in Arid Regions: A Case Study of Administrative Buildings Using Ecotect Simulations	Mohamed Yahia Amran Necib, Khalissa Hamel, Fouzia Meliouh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 997
Y-157	17:00-17:10	Evaluating Natural Lighting Quality in Administrative Buildings Across Different Climatic Regions of Algeria	Mohamed Yahia Amran Necib, Fouzia Meliouh, Khalissa Hamel, Faten Ghanemi	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 999
Y-158	17:17-17:20	CONTRIBUTION TO THE STUDY OF EARTHWORMS IN TWO STATIONS IN SOUK AHRAS, ALGERIA	AOUAMRIA Keltoum, MERGHAD Amina, BOUBSIL Soumaya	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1000
Y-159	17:20-17:30	Analysis of Enzymatic Reactions of Catalase, Glutathione S-Transferase, and Reduced Glutathione to Cr ₂ O ₃ Nanoparticle Exposure in Stramonita haemastoma	Fateh SEDRATI, Hana BOUZAHOUANE, Fadila KHALDI, Mohcen MENAA, Tayeb BOUARROUDJ, Hadjer ZAIDI, Kheireddine OUALI	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1002
Y-160	17:30-17:40	Evaluation of toxic effects of bread-making additives	BEKHOUCHE Ines, DRIOUCHE Youssouf, BEKHOUCHE Nihad, FERFAR Mariem	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1010

Session 1.17			10 NOVEMBER 2024 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-161	17:00-17:10	Numerical and Experimental Comparison of Indentation in Laser Shock Peening on AA2024-T351 Aluminum Alloy	Naoum Halima, Fekirini Hamida, Tayboun Lamisse, Khodja Malika	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, South Africa	Submission 1014
Y-162	17:10-17:20	A Study of Modern Reinforcement Techniques for Concrete Structures to Address Seismic Risks	Khaoula MENNAA	Algeria	Submission 1021
Y-163	17:20-17:30	Histopathologic Evaluation of the Liver and Kidney of Monoammonium Phosphate-Treated Rats	Araar Samia, Khaldi Fadila, Sayah Sarra	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1026
Y-164	17:30-17:40	The antimicrobial properties of Algerian propolis	OUAHAB Amina, GRARA Nedjoud	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1028
Y-165	17:40-17:50	Study of an earth-based mortar. Mechanical behaviour and absorption by capillary action	Bouadellah Feredj, Nabil Abou-Bekr, Mohamed Bencheikh	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1032
Y-166	17:50-18:00	Transforming the Classroom with Mobile Learning, Applications, and Creative Programming	Robert Kosova, Fabiana Cullhaj, Rinela Kapçiu, Anna Maria Kosova, Fatjona Bushi, Taulant Kullolli	Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 1037
Y-167	18:00-18:10	Spiral Hollow Fiber Membrane Contactor for Methylene Blue Separation	Narimene ZEGHOUATI, Said BEY, Abdelatif BELAMRI, Alberto FIGOLI, Alessandra CRISCUOLI, Mohamed BENAMOR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Italy, Italy, Algeria	Submission 1038
Y-168	18:10-18:20	Development of bioactive thiophenic compounds from oxime precursors: sustainable synthesis and pharmacological potential	Chellali Ferial, Datoussaid Yazid, Attar tarik, Cherigui Samir, Julio A. Seijas, M. Pilar Vázquez-Tato	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Spain, Spain	Submission 1048
Y-169	18:20-18:30	The Dynamic Behavior and Stress Distribution Analysis of Sandwich-Core Composite Beams Using Advanced Modal Analysis	Rachid RABEHI, Mohamed RABEHI, Said ZAOUAI, Naas ALLOUT, Yazid CHETBANI, Mohammed OMRANE, Ouassila BAHLOUL, Ali ABBACHE, Mohamed AMIEUR	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1055
Y-170	18:30-18:40	Effect of pH on the Photodegradation of Rhodamine B Using a BaSO ₄ _ZnO Composite Catalyst	AITOUCHE Dounia, IKKOUR Kahina, BOUZIDI Nedjma, ADJOU Ouiza	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1075

Session 1.19			10 NOVEMBER 2024 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-181	18:00-18:10	Impact of Hospital and Industrial Effluents on the Spread of Bacterial Resistance: Challenges and Sustainable Solutions	Mellouk fatma zohra, Saily Linda, Afri Amira, Djamai Zahra, Ali rachedi Soufiane, Arif Saleh, Belbel Fatma, Allem Mohcen	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 700
Y-182	18:18-18:20	Chemoinformatic study of Indenoquinoxaline-phenylacrylohydrazide hybrids as α -amylase inhibitors	Lhoucine Naanaai, Abdellah El Aissouq, Khalil Azzaoui, Hicham Zaitan, Mohammed Bouachrine, Fouad Khalil	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 706
Y-183	18:20-18:30	Impact of Wi-Fi Exposure on Sleep Patterns and Behavior in Rats	SAILI Linda, MELLOUK Fatma Zohra, AFRI Amira, AFRI Salah, ALLEM Mohcen, DJIMAI Zahra, Sofiane Ali Rachedi, BELBEL Fatma	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 709
Y-184	18:30-18:40	Tensile Strength Analysis of Hybrid Aramid/E-Glass Fabric: A Comparative Evaluation with E-Glass and Carbon Fiber Materials	Khmissi BELKAID, Adel DELIOU, Taher GUETTAF TEMAM, Hamza AOUAICHIA, Djamel Edinne GAAGAIA	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 710
Y-185	18:40-18:50	Control of an Electro-energetic System	Toufik Amieur, Abdelhamid Djari, Moussa Sedraoui	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 715
Y-186	18:50-19:00	Design and Synthesis of Innovative Xanthene Derivatives: Toxicity Assessment and Antihyperlipidemic Activity Evaluated In Vivo and In Silico	Mohammed El Mesky, Nazih ouassou, Mohamed tanghourte, Yassine Rhazi, Mohamed Jabha, khallouki farid, Asmae Nakkabi, Ahmed oubair, Znini Mohamed, Driss Chebabe, El Houssine Mabrouk	Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco, Morocco	Submission 725
Y-187	19:00-19:10	Valorization of Citrus waste: Optimization of Bioactive Compounds Extraction and Bioactivity Assessment from Citrus clementina Peels	KADI Ahcene, TEFFANE Mohand, TAIBI Abdeslem, ARROUL Younes, BOUDRIES Hafid, BACHIR-BEY Mostapha, SOUAGUI Samiha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 748
Y-188	19:10-19:20	Analysis of the impact of porosity on the mechanical behavior of advanced composite materials	Ait Atmane Redhwane, Ait Atmane Hassen, Bennai Riadh, HADJI Lazreg	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 806
Y-189	19:20-19:30	Higher order shear deformation for free vibrations functionally imperfect plates	Ait Atmane Redhwane, Ait Atmane Hassen,	Algeria, Algeria,	Submission 807

			Bennai Riadh, HADJI Lazreg	Algeria, Algeria	
Y-190	19:30-19:40	Curie temperature and spontaneous polarization behaviour in $[(\text{LiNbO})_3]$	Hamza Hboub, Noureddine Masaif	Morocco, Morocco	Submission 820

Session 1.20			10 NOVEMBER 2024 18:00-20:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-191	18:00-18:10	The grafting of a biodegradable polymer by a natural catalyst	Amina Mostefai, Choulia Latifa Halloui, Chafika Mostefai, Mahmoud Belalia	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 823
Y-192	18:18-18:20	IN SITU SYNTHESIS OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES IN PECTIN MATRIX FOR THE PREPARATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL AND BIODEGRADABLE FOOD PACKAGING FILMS	Meniche Amel, Chibani Nacéra	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 824
Y-193	18:20-18:30	Using Machine Learning to Identify Fake Profiles on Social Media	Rafik HAMMOU, Nadir MAHAMMED, Imène SAIDI, Karima ZAID	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 842
Y-194	18:30-18:40	Albanian junglans regia l. (walnut bark), chemical composition and biological values	Jona Keri, Lorena Memushaj, Ina Xhangoli	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 845
Y-195	18:40-18:50	Mechanical Response of Silver-Alumina Bimaterial With Interfacial Crack Under Tensile Loading	Tayeboun lamisse, Sellam souad, Fekirini hamida, Bouafia farida	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 890
Y-196	18:50-19:00	Digital Transformation Indicators: A Comparative Study between Algeria and Turkey	Abdelaziz Salah Eddine, Thameur Oussama, Aymane Khachab	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 903
Y-197	19:00-19:10	Biological synthesis of M-phosphates	OUNNOUGHI Hadjer, BOUDEMAGH Djalila, CHEBLI Derradji	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 911
Y-198	19:10-19:20	The Digital Financial Service and Financial Inclusion Nexus: A Short-run and Long-run Analysis of Pakistan	Rahim Bukhsh Shaikh	Pakistan	Submission 960
Y-199	19:20-19:30	Dynamic effect of credit risk management on the financial performance of commercial banks in Pakistan	Samra Saleem Arain	Pakistan	Submission 966
Y-200	19:30-19:40	Impact of Agricultural Credit on Agricultural Production in Pakistan	Salman Sultan, Shahzeb Munir	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 971

Session 1.21			10 NOVEMBER 2024 19:00-21:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
Y-201	19:00-19:10	Impact of Debt Financing on Financial Performance of non-financial firms in Pakistan	Agha Aijaz Khan, Kainat Agha	Pakistan, Pakistan	Submission 972
Y-202	19:11-19:20	The effect of external repair in notched composite laminates (E-Glass/sw905-2)	AMINALLAH Salma, TAYEBOUN Lamisse	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 980
Y-203	19:20-19:30	The effect of mechanical properties of patches on the repair performance of composite structures	AMINALLAH Salma, TAYEBOUN Lamisse	Algeria, Algeria	Submission 983
Y-204	19:30-19:40	Understanding Bankruptcy Risks: An Analysis of the Altman Model in Albania's Banking Sector	Gisjana Tahiri, Besiana Lika	Albania, Albania	Submission 998
Y-205	19:40-19:50	Seismic Response Analysis of Concrete Gravity Dams Considering Soil-Structure Interaction	Djamel Ouzandja, Mokhtar Messaad, Taieb Messaad	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1025
Y-206	19:50-20:00	The study of bifurcations and stability of a linear dynamical system when the fixed point changes from hyperbolic to non-hyperbolic	Valentina Shehu, Dorina Guxholli, Blerta Dervishi	Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 1030
Y-207	20:00-20:10	Effects of the combination of limestone and calcined mud on the behavior of mortar	Hadjer Chenchouna, Samia Hachemi, Boucherit Dalila	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1063
Y-208	20:10-20:20	Goji Berry diet supplementation effect on male rabbit sperm morphology	Gerald Muça, Gabriele Brecchia, Majlind Sulçe, Luigj Trumalaj, Laura Menchetti, Stella Agradi, Enkeleda Ozuni, Xhelil Koleci, Pëllumb Zalla, Egon Andoni, Doriana Beqiraj	Albania, Italy, Albania, Albania, Italy, Italy, Albania, Albania, Albania, Albania	Submission 1072
Y-209	20:20-20:30	Molecular Insights into the Anticancer Effects of Quercetin on Breast Cancer Cells: Cell Cycle Arrest, Apoptosis, and Caspase Modulation	Kebsa Widad, Rouibah Hassiba, Belahcene Samia, Lahouel Mesbah	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Submission 1076
Y-210	20:30-20:40	The Albanian penal policy towards corruption in justice	Erisa Datja, Fioralba Markja	Albania, Albania	Submission 1050
Y-211	20:40-20:50	The research on the impact of changes in human resource management components on employee stress	Sonela STILLO, Gentisa Furxhi	Albania, Albania	Submission 1074
Y-212	20:50-21:00	In-Depth Study of Conformation and Electronic Structure: X-ray Diffraction Coupled with NCI-RDG and NBO Theoretical Analyses of a New Single-Crystal Organic Compound	Nour Eddine Benharkat, Abdelkader Chouaih, Nouridine Boukabcha	Algeria, Algeria, Algeria	Mail Submission 36

Session 2.1			11 NOVEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-1	09:00-09:10	Smarandache Curves Obtained From T- Pedal Curves of A Helix Curve	Süleyman ŞENYURT, Filiz ERTEM KAYA, Davut CANLI	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 3
T-2	09:10-09:20	Türkiye'deki Kadınların Tiktok Kullanımı ve Diğer Sosyal Medya Uygulamaları ile İlişkisi	Ömer ALKAN, Şeyda ÜNVER	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 4
T-3	09:20-09:30	Pandemi Sonrası Evden Çalışma Sıklığıyla İlişkili Sosyodemografik ve Ekonomik Faktörler	Şeyda ÜNVER, Ömer ALKAN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 5
T-4	09:30-09:40	EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF DRAMA ON ENGLISH LEARNING PERCEPTIONS	Rümeysa Küçük, Süleyman Kasap	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 6
T-5	09:40-09:50	Examining the Impact of Drama-based English Language Instruction on Student Attitudes: A Metaphorical Study	Betül Altın, Süleyman Kasap	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 7
T-6	09:50-10:00	Dizel Motorlarda Nanopartikül Yakıt Katkısının Silindir Basıncı Üzerindeki Etkisi: Motor Pistonunda Oluşan Gerilme ve Deformasyon Analizi	Mehmet ÇELİK, Musa AVCI	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 8
T-7	10:00-10:10	MALWARE TRAFFIC ANALYSIS WITH VANILLA NEURAL NETWORK	Nida CANPOLAT, Şengül DOĞAN, Türker TUNCER	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 9
T-8	10:10-10:20	The Effect of Temperature and Molar Ratio on Acidity of DES (Zinc Chloride and Ethylene Glycerol)	Çağlar Mert AYDIN	Turkey	Submission 688
T-9	10:20-10:30	Sonlu Elemanlar Yöntemi Kullanılarak Ti-6Al-4V'nin Yüksek Hızlı Mikro Frezelenmesinde Kesme Kuvvetlerinin İncelenmesi	Aybars MAHMAT	Turkey	Submission 689
T-10	10:30-10:40	The Impact of Country Economy, Population, and Primary Energy Consumed on CO2 Estimation: ML Approach for Türkiye Data	Yasemin Ayaz Atalan	Turkey	Submission 694

Session 2.2			11 NOVEMBER 2024 09:00-11:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-11	09:00-09:10	Production of Cu Based Composite Materials: Powder Metallurgical Fabrication and Microstructural Characterization	Mehmet Akkaş	Turkey	Submission 697
T-12	09:10-09:20	İndirgenmiş Grafen Oksit Nanopartikül Katkılı Yakıtların Silindir Basıncı ve Yanma Karakteristikleri Üzerindeki Etkileri	Mehmet ÇELİK, Cihan BAYINDIRLI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 713
T-13	09:20-09:30	5-Sülfosalisilik asit ve 2-Amino-(4/5)-süstitüepiridin İçeren Tuzların Antimikrobiyal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Cengiz Yenikaya, Aysel Gülbandılar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 722
T-14	09:30-09:40	5-Sülfosalisilik asit ve 2-Amino-(4/6)-metilpiridin İçeren Tuzların Antimikrobiyal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Cengiz Yenikaya, Aysel Gülbandılar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 723
T-15	09:40-09:50	5-Sülfosalisilik asit ve 2-Amino-3-süstitüepiridin İçeren Tuzların Antimikrobiyal Aktivitelerinin İncelenmesi	Halil İlkimen, Cengiz Yenikaya, Aysel Gülbandılar	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 724
T-16	09:50-10:00	Mobil Uygulamaların Türkçe Öğretiminde Kullanımı: Kahoot Örneği	Ahmet Karabulut	Turkey	Submission 726
T-17	10:00-10:10	Özel Gereksinimli Bireylerin Dil Eğitiminde Yardımcı Teknolojilerin Kullanımı	Ahmet Karabulut	Turkey	Submission 728
T-18	10:10-10:20	Determination of radiation shielding properties in BaO–Fe2O3–SrO–B2O3 glass systems doped with Bi2O3	Selim KAYA	Turkey	Submission 729
T-19	10:20-10:30	Karaman (Gödet) Sulama Tesisi Takviye YAS (Yeraltı Suyu) Kuyularının Güneş Enerjisi ile Çalıştırılması	İslam Çağrı AVARA, Selmin ENER RÜŞEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 737
T-20	10:30-10:40	Minimalist Estetiğin Reklam Tasarımında Yeri ve Önemi	Birsen Çeken, Merve Ersan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 743

Session 2.3			11 NOVEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-21	10:00-10:10	Cebimizdeki Sağlık: Beslenme ve Sağlıklı Yaşam Mobil Uygulamaları	Reyhan İrkin, Selin Özelsancak Yavuz, Şevval Gülce	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 746
T-22	10:10-10:20	TÜRKİYE’NİN BİYOKÜTLE ENERJİ POTANSİYELİ	Nurullah AKGÜN, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 756
T-23	10:20-10:30	A Comparative Study of Various Metaheuristic Optimization Techniques for Stabilizing a Fractional Order PID Controller	Uğur Demiroğlu, Bilal Şenol	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 759
T-24	10:30-10:40	Tuning the Overshoot in Step Response with Metaheuristic Approaches using the PD Controller Lack of the Integral Effect	Bilal Şenol, Uğur Demiroğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 760
T-25	10:40-10:50	Krank-Biyel Mekanizmasında Gaz Kuvvetlerini Dikkate Alarak Farklı Yükleme Şartlarının Hız Değişimine Etkisi	Çağlar SEVİM	Turkey	Submission 774
T-26	10:50-11:00	DP 1000 Çeliğinin Isıl İşlem Sonrası Sertlik Davranışı	Cihangir Tevfik Sezgin	Turkey	Submission 781
T-27	11:00-11:10	Demir-Çelik Cürüflarının Kullanımı	Cihangir Tevfik Sezgin	Turkey	Submission 782
T-28	11:10-11:20	Ekran Bağımsız Grafik Tasarım: Geleceğin Esnek Arayüzleri	Merve Ersan	Turkey	Submission 783
T-29	11:20-11:30	C6'dan C45'e kadar olan petrol fraksiyonları için Kritik Özelliklerinin karbon sayısına bağlı olarak Hesaplanmasında Kullanılacak Model Denklemlerin Geliştirilmesi mevcut modeller ile mukayesesi	İnci TÜRK TOĞRUL, Hasan TOĞRUL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 791
T-30	11:30-11:40	C6'dan C45'e Kadar Olan Petrol Fraksiyonları için Buhar Basıncı, Spesifik Gravite, Molekül Ağırlığı Ve Asentrik Faktörün Karbon Sayısına Bağlı Olarak Hesaplanmasında Kullanılacak Model Denklemlerin Geliştirilmesi Mevcut Modeller ile Mukayesesi	İnci TÜRK TOĞRUL, Hasan TOĞRUL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 792

Session 2.4			11 NOVEMBER 2024 10:00-12:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-31	10:00-10:10	Evaluation of Wear Behavior of Al2024 Alloy Produced via Powder Metallurgy Using the Taguchi Method	Serhatcan Berk AKÇAY, Temel VAROL, Fatih ERDEMİR, Mücahit KOCAMAN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 793
T-32	10:10-10:20	Investigation of the effects of hot-pressing temperature on Ti-B4C composite materials produced with 10% B4C reinforcement	Serhatcan Berk AKÇAY, Temel VAROL, Oğuzhan ÇUVALCI, Mücahit KOCAMAN, Gizem ATİK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 794
T-33	10:20-10:30	BRAIN BASED CLASSIFICATION WITH IMAGE PROCESSING AND DEEP ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE METHODS IN MATLAB SOFTWARE ENVIRONMENT	Ali Berkan Ural, Mehmet Can Çalım	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 796
T-34	10:30-10:40	Alanya Dim Çayı Taşkın Risk Analizi	Mehmet Dikici	Turkey	Submission 798
T-35	10:40-10:50	Dynamic Analysis of a Simply Supported Euler-Bernoulli Beam on a Two-Parameter Elastic Foundation with Moving Oscillator: Effects of Varying Shear Foundation Modulus	Mehmet Akif Koç, Mustafa Eroğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 810
T-36	10:50-11:00	Hyperelastic Strips with Null Directrix	Tunahan TURHAN, Gözde ÖZKAN TÜKEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 812
T-37	11:00-11:10	Characterization of Hyperelastic Strips with Pseudo-Null Base Curves	Tunahan TURHAN, Gözde ÖZKAN TÜKEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 813
T-38	11:10-11:20	Determining the Effect of Adverse Weather Conditions on Radar Measurement Values	Tarık Ünler, Levent Seyfi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 814
T-39	11:20-11:30	Life Cycle Assessment of Display Cabinet Production	Hüseyin Ok, Murat Eyvaz, Mihriban Civan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 821
T-40	11:30-11:40	Bir hastanedeki enerji tüketimi ve karbon ayak izinin belirlenmesi	Selmin ENER RÜŞEN, Aydın RÜŞEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 822

Session 2.5			11 NOVEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-41	11:00-11:10	Çinko sektöründe oluşan liç atığının karakterizasyonu	Aydın RÜŞEN, Fatma ÖZEL	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 825
T-42	11:11-11:20	Görüntü İşleme ile Demirözü (Bayburt) Çevresinde Yüzeyleyen Ofiyolitlerin Tespiti	Mustafa Alptekin Engin, Murat Camuzcuoğlu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 827
T-43	11:20-11:30	Çalışkan Göleti (Akdağmadeni/Yozgat) Göl Alanı, Sağ ve Sol Sahillerinin Geçirimliliğinin Değerlendirilmesi	Mehmet Özçelik	Turkey	Submission 830
T-44	11:30-11:40	DENETİM RAPORU GECİKMESİNİ ETKİLEYEN FAKTÖRLER: BORSA İSTANBUL ÖRNEĞİ	Aysel Öztürkçü Akçay, Gamze Sevimli Örgün	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 841
T-45	11:40-11:50	EFFORTS TO MODERNIZE EDUCATION IN TURKESTAN UNDER THE LEADERSHIP OF ISMAIL GASPIRALI: THE USÛL-I CEDID MOVEMENT	Şengül Büyükboyacı	Turkey	Submission 844
T-46	11:50-12:00	Türkiye'de Tektonizma ve Kabuk Yapısı İlişkisi	Mustafa Nuri Dolmaz, Ömer Elitok	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 846
T-47	12:00-12:10	Olumlu Belediye İmajının Seçimlere Yönelik Tutum Üzerindeki Etkisi	İbrahim AYDIN, Reha SAYDAN, Zübeyir ÇELİK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 847
T-48	12:10-12:20	A Comprehensive Review of Fuzzy Numbers and Linear Operators	Sevilay KIRCI SERENBAY	Turkey	Submission 849
T-49	12:20-12:30	KONFEKSİYON İŞLETMELERİNDEKİ KESİM MAKİNALARINDA VERİMLİLİĞE ETKİ EDEN KESİM PARAMETRELERİ	Ayça Gürarda	Turkey	Submission 851
T-50	12:30-12:40	Rüzgâr Enerjisi Santrallerinde İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği	Mahsum KAZAN, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 852

Session 2.6			11 NOVEMBER 2024 11:00-13:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-51	11:00-11:10	Determination of The Most Suitable Rooting Medium For 'Marsol' Chestnut Cultivar in Plantform Bioreactor System	Nihan Buse Akbulut, Burak Akyüz, İbrahim Halil Hatipoğlu	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 854
T-52	11:11-11:20	Isparta İlindeki Hava Kalitesi Verilerinin İncelenmesi ve İstatiksel Değerlendirilmesi	Muhammet Yunus PAMUKOĞLU	Turkey	Submission 855
T-53	11:20-11:30	Dut ve Biyoaktif Bileşenler	Sudenaz Binektaş, Nazan Tokatlı Demirok	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 859
T-54	11:30-11:40	Dut Yaprağının Antidiyabetik Etkisi	Sudenaz Binektaş, Nazan Tokatlı Demirok	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 861
T-55	11:40-11:50	SOSYAL MEDYA PAZARLAMA ETKİNLİKLERİNİN MARKANIN FARKINDALIĞI VE TUTUM ÜZERİNDEKİ ETKİSİ	Bulut DÜLEK, Hamza KOÇAK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 866
T-56	11:50-12:00	İÇSEL PAZARLAMA VE KURUMSAL İMAJ ALGILAMALARININ DEMOGRAFİK DEĞİŞKENLER AÇISINDAN ANALİZİ VE İÇSEL PAZARLAMANNIN KURUMSAL İMAJ ÜZERİNE ETKİSİ	Bulut DÜLEK	Turkey	Submission 869
T-57	12:00-12:10	Blockchain-Enabled Risk Management in Supply Chains: A p-q-Quasirung Orthopair Fuzzy SIWEC Analysis	Ahmet Çalık	Turkey	Submission 870
T-58	12:10-12:20	Girişimciliğin İhracat Üzerindeki Etkisi: Seçilmiş OECD Ülkeleri Üzerinde Bir Uygulama	İlyas Kays İmamoğlu, Yusuf Esmer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 871
T-59	12:20-12:30	TRAFİK SUÇUNU ETKİLEYEN SOSYO-EKONOMİK FAKTÖRLER: TÜRKİYE ÖRNEĞİ (2010-2020)	Ufuk IŞIK	Turkey	Submission 877
T-60	12:30-12:40	Havran Barajı (Balıkesir-Havran) Chironomidae (Diptera-Insecta) Faunasının Belirlenmesi Üzerine Bir Çalışma	Tuğrul Öntürk	Turkey	Submission 881

Session 2.7			11 NOVEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-61	12:00-12:10	Demografik Özelliklere Göre Tüketici Boykot Davranışının İncelenmesi	Zübeyir ÇELİK, Reha SAYDAN, İbrahim AYDIN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 882
T-62	12:11-12:20	TNT Patlaması Altında Çelik Lifli Betonun Darbe Dayanımı: RHT Modeli	Mehmet Hanifi ALKAYIŞ, Celalettin BAŞYİĞİT	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 883
T-63	12:20-12:30	Yenilenebilir Enerji Kaynaklarının Avantajları, Dezavantajları ve Ekolojik Etkileri	Aylin KOCAÇİFTÇİ, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 888
T-64	12:30-12:40	Quantum-Augmented AI: A Comprehensive Analysis of Emerging Paradigms and Applications	Musa Ataş, Bashar Alhajahmad	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 889
T-65	12:40-12:50	Glioblastoma Hücre Hattında (Z)-2,3-bis (4-nitrophenyl)-acrylonitrile (ZNPA) ile PON1 Aktivasyonunun IL-6 ve HIF-1a Protein Seviyeleri ile İlişkisinin Belirlenmesi	Armin Attar, Hacı Ahmet Kılıç, Özen Özensoy Güler, Ender Şimşek	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 891
T-66	12:50-13:00	AlN ve ZnO Bazlı Nanoakışkan İçeren Kabuk Borulu Isı Değiştiricinin Sayısal Analizi	Murat ÖZTÜRK, Erdem ÇİFTÇİ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 895
T-67	13:00-13:10	Kamuda Sıfır Atık Yönetimi ve Enerji Verimliliği Algısı	Selmin ENER RÜŞEN, Aydın RÜŞEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 910
T-68	13:10-13:20	Implementation Expressing Compositions of a Positive Integer	Busra Al, Mustafa Alkan	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 10
T-69	13:20-13:30	Implementation Expressing Color Compositions of a Positive Integer	Busra Al, Mustafa Alkan	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 11
T-70	13:30-13:40	Examining the Concept of “Addiction” in the Context of the Problem of Freedom	Zeynep KANTARCI BİNGÖL	Turkey	Mail Submission 12

Session 2.8			11 NOVEMBER 2024 12:00-14:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-71	12:00-12:10	Esrar Kullanımı ve İnsan Hakları: Ayrımcılık, Ceza Politikaları ve Dini Perspektifler	Abdullah ELMAS	Turkey	Submission 681
T-72	12:11-12:20	KARBON/GRAFEN BAZLI ELEKTROKATALİZÖR GELİŞTİRMESİ VE HİDROJEN EVRİM REAKSİYONU PERFORMANSI İNCELENMESİ	Burçin Şahin, Alpay Şahin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 745
T-73	12:20-12:30	Kullanılabilirlik Testleri Üzerine: Veri Toplamının Kullanıcı Tasarımına Etkisi	Semih Delil	Turkey	Submission 848
T-74	12:30-12:40	Wind Energy Systems Optimization Using Particle Swarm	Safa Fadhil, Ercan Aykut	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 885
T-75	12:40-12:50	Hidroelektrik Santrallerde İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği: Çalışma Prensipleri, Riskler ve Önlemler	Aylin KOCAÇİFTÇİ, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 886
T-76	12:50-13:00	Güneş Enerjisi Santrallerinde İş Sağlığı ve Güvenliği	Emir ÜSTÜN, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 887
T-77	13:00-13:10	An Investigation on the Stability of Time-Delayed q-Fractional Singular Systems	Yener ALTUN	Turkey	Submission 896
T-78	13:10-13:20	Evaluation of Electric and Magnetic Field Measurements in Isparta Province	Ozlem Coskun	Turkey	Submission 897
T-79	13:20-13:30	Economic Importance and Uses of Safflower (Carthamus tinctorius L.)	Betül GIDİK	Turkey	Submission 898
T-80	13:30-13:40	TiO ₂ Takviyeli Hibrit Kompozit Malzemelerde Çekme Dayanımlarının Deneysel Olarak İncelenmesi	Raşit Koray Ergün, Mehmet Emin Demir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 899

Session 2.9			11 NOVEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-81	13:00-13:10	Effect of Aluminum Waste Powder Reinforcement on Strength Performance and Electrical Conductivity of Cement Mortar	Ahmet FİLAZİ, Muharrem PUL, Rüstem YILMAZEL	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 904
T-82	13:11-13:20	Yüksek Sönümlenme Özelliklerine Sahip Kauçuk Karışımlarının İncelenmesi	Zeynep Yıldız, Özlem Çavdar, Ali Karimzadeh Naghshineh	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 905
T-83	13:20-13:30	Aydınlatma Sistemlerinde Enerji Tasarrufu	Emir ÜSTÜN, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 907
T-84	13:30-13:40	Simulation of a PMSG Wind Turbine under Variable Wind Speed Conditions	Kerim KARABACAK	Turkey	Submission 908
T-85	13:40-13:50	Smart Temperature Monitoring and Control Using SBC Boards and IoT Technology	Bashar ALHAJAHMAD, Musa Ataş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 909
T-86	13:50-14:00	Yonga Levhalarda Yoğunluk ve Kalınlık Parametrelerinin Elastikiyet Modülü Üzerindeki Etkisi	Rıfat Kurt	Turkey	Submission 913
T-87	14:00-14:10	Tilapia Balığı Kullanılarak Akuaponik Sistemlerde Marul Üretimi	Muhammet Yunus PAMUKOĞLU, Halit BAYRAK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 924
T-88	14:10-14:20	Otomotiv Sektörünün 11. ve 12. Kalkınma Planlarındaki Yeri	Buket Karatop, Sezer Seçkin Erdem, Mehmet Sinan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 927
T-89	14:20-14:30	Eğitim Stratejilerini Belirlemede Büyük ve Küçük Verinin Önemi	Buket Karatop	Turkey	Submission 929
T-90	14:30-14:40	Impact of Perceived Stress on Seafarers' Performance: The Role of Resilience in High-Stress Maritime Scenarios	Cenk Ay	Turkey	Submission 933

Session 2.10			11 NOVEMBER 2024 13:00-15:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-91	13:00-13:10	Değişken Tipteki Elastik Zemin Üzerindeki Nano Kirişlerin Statik Analizi	Uğur Kafkas, Gökhan Güçlü	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 935
T-92	13:11-13:20	Optimization of Flexural Strength of Parts Produced from ABS-Like Resin Using Stereolithography	ÇERLEK Ömer, HAN Kubilay, TÜYLÜ Adem	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 936
T-93	13:20-13:30	Küresel Trendlere Yerel Dokunuş: İç Mekan Tasarımında Küyerelleşme	İrem Bekar	Turkey	Submission 937
T-94	13:30-13:40	İNSAN-DOĞA-SANAT BAĞLAMINDA SANATÇI YAKLAŞIMLARI	Seda DİLAY	Turkey	Mail Submission 13
T-95	13:40-13:50	Wave Packet Clustering of Self-focusing Free Particle	Zalihe Ozcakmakli Turker	Turkey	Submission 856
T-96	13:50-14:00	YENİLENEBİLİR ENERJİ KAYNAKLARININ AZERBAIJAN EKONOMİSİ BAKIMINDAN DEĞERLENDİRİLMESİ	Anar AGHAZADA, Suna MUĞAN ERTUĞRAL	Azerbaijan, Turkey	Submission 874
T-97	14:00-14:10	Eriyik Yığıma Modellemesi Yönteminin Uygulama Alanları	Osman Ülker	Turkey	Submission 901
T-98	14:10-14:20	Almanca Öğretmenliği Eğitiminde MEB Tavsiyeli Web 2.0 Araçları ve Öğretmen Adaylarının Geri Bildirimleri	Ayşe Arslan Çavuşoğlu	Turkey	Submission 912
T-99	14:20-14:30	Rüzgar Türbin Sistemlerinde Ağırlıklı Geometrik Merkez Yöntemi ile Tasarlanan PI-PD Kontrolü	Abdullah Turan, Hebat Günel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 928
T-100	14:30-14:40	Eye-Tracking as an Indicator of Depressive Emotional States in Virtual Reality: An Explainable Artificial Intelligence Approach	Meryem Bekler, Murat Yılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 932

Session 2.11			11 NOVEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-101	14:00-14:10	Metilen Mavisinin Sulardan Metal/Metaloksit Nanopartiküllerle Giderilmesi	Kadriye Özlem SAYGI	Turkey	Submission 938
T-102	14:11-14:20	Nanopartiküllerin Farklı Şekilleri ve Uygulama Alanları Üzerindeki Etkileri	Kadriye Özlem SAYGI	Turkey	Submission 939
T-103	14:20-14:30	SoyBean-CNN-ViT: Soybean Seed Classification with Fusion of CNN and ViT	Mustafa YURDAKUL, Şakir TAŞDEMİR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 940
T-104	14:30-14:40	Soğuk Dövme Makinasıyla Üretilen Namlu İçin Görüntü Mozaikleme Uygulaması	Samet KALIN	Turkey	Submission 941
T-105	14:40-14:50	Gender Recognition from voice using machine learning algorithms	Mustafa YURDAKUL, Şakir TAŞDEMİR	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 942
T-106	14:50-15:00	An Approach to Generate Synthetic Image Data for Free-Space Optical Communication Turbulence Disturbance using DCGAN	Emre YÜKSEK, Kemal ADEM	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 944
T-107	15:00-15:10	QUANTUM COMPUTING AND ITS EVALUATION IN CYBER SECURITY	Ramazan Yasin Çiftçi, Ahmet Ali Süzen	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 945
T-108	15:10-15:20	Bulanık Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Teknikleri ile Sürdürülebilir Tedarikçi Seçimi	Aliye Ayça Supçiller, Ceren Kaplan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 951
T-109	15:20-15:30	İş Yükü ve Duygusal Emek Kavramları Arasındaki İlişkinin Bibliyometrik Analiz Yöntemi ile İncelenmesi	Yashar GULİYEV, Abdullah YILMAZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 952
T-110	15:30-15:40	Mechanical Properties of Ti Alloys Produced by Additive Manufacturing	Alican YAKIN	Turkey	Submission 957

Session 2.12			11 NOVEMBER 2024 14:00-16:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-111	14:00-14:10	BARET KAZIKLARDA YÜK UYGULAMA YÖNÜNÜN YANAL YÜK KAPASİTESİNE OLAN ETKİSİNİN MODEL DENEYLERLE ANALİZİ	Ahmet TOPALOĞLU, Yakup TÜREDİ, Murat ÖRNEK	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 958
T-112	14:11-14:20	Interconnected Split-Ring-Resonator Fork-Shaped Microstrip Antenna for 2.4 GHz Wi-Fi Applications	Yağız Haktan Gözkaman, Merih Palandöken	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 961
T-113	14:20-14:30	Çokgen ayrıt kesitine sahip kafes yapıların enerji absorbe etme verimliliklerinin deneysel incelenmesi	Muhammet Muaz Yalçın	Turkey	Submission 962
T-114	14:30-14:40	2018-2024 Yılları Arasında Dijital Öyküleme İle İlgili Yapılmış Çalışmalar	İrem Cansu DEMİR, Murat ÇETİNKAYA	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 963
T-115	14:40-14:50	Intelligent Rail Transportation Systems and Developments in Literature	Eyyüp TAŞKAYA, Bahadır Furkan KINACI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 967
T-116	14:50-15:00	Proton Değişim Membranlı Yakıt Hücresinin Matematiksel Modellenmesi: Literatüre Genel Bakış	Eyyüp TAŞKAYA, Bahadır Furkan KINACI	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 968
T-117	15:00-15:10	Depremlerin Enerji Üretim ve Tüketimi Üzerindeki Etkileri: 6 Şubat Örneği	Edip TAŞKESEN, Hamza ALAHMAD, Elif Nur BİLEN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 973
T-118	15:10-15:20	Relaxing Frequency Music Application Activated by Pulse Detection	Emre AVUÇLU, Hüseyin ELDEM, Zeynep İLHAN, Ali Mert ATASOY	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 976
T-119	15:20-15:30	Bir Merkezli Kinetik Enerji İntegralinin Guseinov $\psi\alpha$ -ETO' ları Kullanılarak Analitik Olarak Hesaplanması	E. Çopuroğlu	Turkey	Submission 977
T-120	15:30-15:40	Theoretical study of thermal conductivity of GaN using Callaway approximation	E. Çopuroğlu, B.A. Mamedov	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 978

Session 2.13			11 NOVEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-121	15:00-15:10	Ağaç İşleme Endüstrisinde Toz ve Gürültü Problemi	Özcan Gül, Mustafa Korkmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 981
T-122	15:11-15:20	Fluid Modern World and Digital Social Media: The Easiest Way to Stay Connected or Isolation?	Serdar ÜNAL	Turkey	Submission 987
T-123	15:20-15:30	The Happiness Industry in the Modern Consumer Society: Infinite Desires and the Production of Dissatisfied Citizens	Serdar ÜNAL	Turkey	Submission 988
T-124	15:30-15:40	The Reproduction of Fears in the Age of Uncertainty: The Normalization of the "Other" and Social Exclusion	Serdar ÜNAL	Turkey	Submission 989
T-125	15:40-15:50	Kütüphane Kaynaklarına Erişimi Kolaylaştıran Metaverse Evreninde Tasarlanan Sanal Kütüphane: MetisLand	Faruk Oral, Ümmühan Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 991
T-126	15:50-16:00	Sanal Öğrenci Toplulukları: MetaBC Evreni	Onur Usalan, Ümmühan Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 992
T-127	16:00-16:10	Gemini Yapay Zekâ Arayüzünün Kullanılabilirlik İncelemesi	İrem Damar, Ümmühan Avcı	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 993
T-128	16:10-16:20	Comparison of microstructure and hardness properties of pre-rolled and post-rolled quenched unalloyed powder metal steel containing 2% Mo by weight	Mehmet Akif ERDEN, Harun ÇUĞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1001
T-129	16:20-16:30	Bilişsel radyo ile verimli spektrum kullanımı	Esin YAVUZ	Turkey	Submission 1003
T-130	16:30-16:40	ANALYSIS OF BLUE FILTER COATINGS FOR DIGITAL SCREEN PROTECTION	Hülya KURU MUTLU	Turkey	Submission 1006

Session 2.14			11 NOVEMBER 2024 15:00-17:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-131	15:00-15:10	Muz Kabuğunun Kararma Sürecinde Spektral Değişimlerin İzlenmesi	Mahmut Durgun, Yeliz Durgun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1007
T-132	15:11-15:20	MgO ve B4C takviyeli Al1050 kompozitlerin işlenebilirliğinde takviye malzemeleri ve takım geometrisinin etkisi	Muharrem Pul, Tuncay Şimşek	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1008
T-133	15:20-15:30	Rehabilitation of Side Walls of Simple Timber Barn Model with Steel Sheet	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 1011
T-134	15:30-15:40	Effect of Utilizing Central X-Type Wooden Braces in “Serendi” on Modal Parameters	Furkan Günday	Turkey	Submission 1012
T-135	15:40-15:50	R&D EXPENDITURE TRENDS IN TURKEY OVER TIME: AN INDEX-BASED ANALYSIS FOR THE PERIOD 1990-2021	Cengiz GAZELOĞLU, Eren ERKİLİÇ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1017
T-136	15:50-16:00	EXAMINING THE HISTORICAL THINKING SKILL LEVELS OF MIDDLE SCHOOL STUDENTS	Hüseyin BAYRAM	Turkey	Submission 1022
T-137	16:00-16:10	İklim Krizi, Enerji Tüketimi ve Artan Sağlık Riskleri	Mahsum KAZAN, Hakan DUMRUL, Edip TAŞKESEN	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1023
T-138	16:10-16:20	Moda Tasarımında Renk Tahmini	Muazzez Çetiner	Turkey	Submission 1027
T-139	16:20-16:30	Preliminary pollination biology results of some Linaria Mill. species from Turkey	Burak Şahin, Ferhat Celep, Yasin Bahat, Bayram Atasagun, Fatih Dikmen, Osman Tugay, Metin Armağan, Deniz Ulukuş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1029
T-140	16:30-16:40	Optimization of PCR Analysis Based on iPBS Markers for the Determination of Genetic Diversity of Salvia L.	Esra Nur ÇİFTCİ, Ferhat Celep, Yasin BAHAT, Aras TÜRKOĞLU, Deniz ULUKUŞ	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1031

Session 2.15			11 NOVEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-141	16:00-16:10	A Brief Review of Forensic Entomological Process and Terminology	Aysel Kekilliođlu	Turkey	Submission 1033
T-142	16:10-16:20	Agricultural Production-Environmental Awareness Analysis: Ürgüp Research	Serap Özer, Aysel Kekilliođlu, Esra Albaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1034
T-143	16:20-16:30	Boyalı Ahşap Malzemede Delaminasyon Mekanizmaları ve Önleyici Stratejiler	İzham Kılınç	Turkey	Submission 1039
T-144	16:30-16:40	Mermer Aramasında Jeolojik Uzaktan Algılama Uygulamaları, Balçıkhisar (Çumra-Konya) Örneđi	Kubilay Uysal, Hatice Selcen Dinçer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1040
T-145	16:40-16:50	Comparative Analysis of CatBoost and BiLSTM Models for Day-Ahead Electricity Consumption Forecasting: A Case Study of Aydın, Denizli, and Muđla Regions in Turkey	Hakan Elbaş, Turgay Tugay Bilgin	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1044
T-146	16:50-17:00	Konya Güneyindeki Mermer Sahalarında Yerbilişim Uygulamaları	Kubilay Uysal, Ramazan Yıldırım	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1047
T-147	17:00-17:10	İşletmelerde İşe Alım Sürecinde Karşılaşılan Sorunlara İlişkin Bir Araştırma	Cheikh Mohamed CHEİKH MOHAMED, Abdullah YILMAZ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1049
T-148	17:17-17:20	Hüyük (Konya) ve Çevresindeki Su Kaynaklarının Hidro-kimyasal Özellikleri	Şehnaz Şener, Erhan Şener	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1052
T-149	17:20-17:30	Different applications of AI for wind energy forecasting	Abbas Alkachachi, Ercan Aykut	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1053
T-150	17:30-17:40	Mermer Sahalarında Ön Araştırma için Jeolojik Uzaktan Algılama Uygulamaları, Akören (Konya) Örneđi	Kubilay Uysal, Alperen Şentürk	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1054

Session 2.16			11 NOVEMBER 2024 16:00-18:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-151	16:00-16:10	Sarıgöl (Manisa) Bölgesinin Paleosismolojik Özelliklerinin İncelenmesi	Ahmet Dumlupınar, Kubilay Uysal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1061
T-152	16:10-16:20	Çobandere (Malatya) Bölgesinin Linyit Potansiyelinin Uzaktan Algılama Bulguları	Muhammet Said Kördiş, Kubilay Uysal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1066
T-153	16:20-16:30	Beverage Cooling System Using Thermoelectric Technology in a Smart Table	İsak Berkay İncu, Ahmet Çifci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1067
T-154	16:30-16:40	Eskibalıklı (Çanakkale-Biga) Kalsit Ocağı Jeolojik Uzaktan Algılama Bulguları	İbrahim Giray Kaya, Kubilay Uysal	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1069
T-155	16:40-16:50	Effect of heat treatments applied after deformation on hardness and microstructure properties of iron-based powder metal steel containing Mo	Mehmet Akif ERDEN, Harun ÇUĞ	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1070
T-156	16:50-17:00	Effect of humidity on square shaped plastic fasteners	Orkun Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 1077
T-157	17:00-17:10	Effect of lamel thickness on christmas tree shaped plastic fasteners	Orkun Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 1078
T-158	17:17-17:20	Separable Variables and Fourier Approximations in Solving the Euler-Tricomi Equation	Münevver Tuz	Turkey	Submission 828
T-159	17:20-17:30	LOW SPEED IMPACT DAMAGE RESPONSE OF HYBRID FIBER FABRIC REINFORCED GLIDER WING	Esat KAHRAMAN, Mustafa TAŞYÜREK	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1019
T-160	17:30-17:40	Comparison of Deep Learning Architectures to Evaluate the Effect of COVID-19 on Electricity Consumption	Hisham A. Hamza, Ali Ajder, Ramazan Ayaz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1045

Session 2.17			11 NOVEMBER 2024 17:00-19:00		
P.-NO	Time Interval	Title	Author Names	Country	Submission ID
T-161	17:00-17:10	Optical properties of spin coating deposited copper oxide thin films for solar cell applications	Şilan BATURAY, Serap YIGIT GEZGIN, Hamdi Sukur KILIC	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1035
T-162	17:10-17:20	Numerical analysis of the thin film solar cell modelled based on antimony doped copper oxide	Serap YIGIT GEZGIN, Şilan BATURAY, Hamdi Sukur KILIC	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1036
T-163	17:20-17:30	Effects on Geopolymer Mortars of The Blast-Furnace Slags Obtained from Different Regions	Özlem Çavdar, Hülya Temizer	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1046
T-164	17:30-17:40	Elektromanyetik Alanlar ve Yenilenebilir Enerji Sistemlerinin Sağlık Üzerindeki Etkileri	Servet ERSOY, Hakan DUMRUL, Fatih ARLI	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1060
T-165	17:40-17:50	Comparison of the activities of carbonitrile derivatives molecules against Colorectal cancer	Şaban ERDOĞAN, Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 33
T-166	17:50-18:00	Evaluating the Efficacy of Phenylalanine Derivatives Against Hepatitis B	Koray SAYIN, Burak TÜZÜN	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 34
T-167	18:00-18:10	Transformer Tabanlı Modellerle Türkçe Tweetlerdeki Argo Dilin Tespiti	Zeynep Şebnem Üzmez, Sinem Akyol	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1013
T-168	18:10-18:20	Nutrient-Pathogen Interactions in Agriculture: Mechanisms, Relationships, and Sustainable Practices	Ibrahim Isse Ali, Galad Barre Yusuf, Abdikadir Musa Jama	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1015
T-169	18:20-18:30	ORGANIC METHODS OF FIGHTING AGAINST VARROA PARASITES	Nuray ŞAHİNLER, Sibel ALAPALA DEMİRHAN, Cristina POP	Turkey, Turkey, Romania	Submission 1079
T-170	18:30-18:40	ADHD Bireylerin EEG Sinyalleri ile Biyometrik Tanımlanması: Frontal Lob Tabanlı 1D-CNN, EMD ve t-SNE Yaklaşımı	Rümeysa Nur TEMİR, Kutlucan GÖRÜR	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 35
T-171	18:40-18:50	Integration of Proteus and LabVIEW for Open-Loop DC Motor Control with Position and Speed Feedback	Serhat Küçükdermenci	Turkey	Submission 1041
T-172	18:50-19:00	Real-Time Speed Control System: PID Tuning and Visualization with Proteus and LabVIEW	Serhat Küçükdermenci	Turkey	Submission 1043
T-173	19:00-19:10	Autonomous Measuring Of Poultry Weights	Yasin Aydin, Metin Demirtas	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 1080
T-174	19:10-19:20	Eğitimde Yapay Zeka Kullanımının Fırsatları, Zorlukları ve Stratejik Öneriler Üzerine Bir Değerlendirme	Mustafa Kurtoğlu, Tuğba Koç	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 969